

in IR26 was low. In plots planted to IR26, infection started at the border.

Low RTV infection in IR26 can be explained by the inability of RTBV-infected plants to serve as virus sources for spread of RTV infection and to the cultivar's resistance to RTSV. □

Resistance of rice varieties to rice tungro virus (RTV) and its green leafhopper (GLH) vector in Tamil Nadu, India

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We screened 12 commonly grown rice varieties against RTV and GLH *Nephotettix virescens* Distant in the greenhouse.

Seedlings (15 d old, 20/variety) were inoculated with RTV by releasing three viruliferous vectors on each test plant for a 24-h inoculation feeding. Inoculated plants were kept in an insect-proof cage for symptom expression. Infected seedlings were counted and infection severity graded 25 d after inoculation.

The same varieties were screened against GLH. Pregerminated seeds

Reaction^a of rice varieties to RTV and green leafhopper. Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Rice tungro virus				Green leafhopper	
	Severity rating	Infected plants (%)	Scale based on percentage of infected phnts ^b	Reaction	Scale ^b	Reaction
PTB18	1	0	0	R	1	HR
IET6262	1	0	0	R	1	HR
TNAU13613	5	30	3	I	5	MR
IR26	7	40	5	I	5	MR
IR28	7	40	5	I	3	R
IR29	5	40	5	I	3	R
IR30	3	30	3	I	3	R
IR36	3	20	3	I	5	MR
IR50	1	0	0	R	5	MR
IR52	5	20	3	I	3	R
IR54	3	10	1	R	3	R
TN1	9	90	9	S	9	HS

^aHR = highly resistant, R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, I = intermediate, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible. ^bBy the Standard evaluation system for rice.

were sown 3 cm apart in 20-cm rows in 50- × 40- × 10-cm wooden flats with 7-cm-deep soil. One week after sowing, the seedlings were thinned to 15/row and the flats transferred to 60- × 45- × 15-cm galvanized iron trays filled 10 cm deep with water. The trays were covered with an insect-proof cage.

Seedlings were infested with second- and third-instar nymphs of *N. virescens*. Plants containing nymphs were gently tapped over the seedlings so that 4-5 nymphs were released per seedling. Damage was rated 6 d after

infestation, when susceptible check TN1 seedlings were severely damaged.

PTB18, IET6262, and IR50 did not show symptoms of RTV infection (see table). IR54 was resistant to infection, with a severity value of 3. This is the first report of IET6262 showing RTV resistance under artificial inoculation. Other varieties showed moderate resistance.

PTB18 and IET6262 were highly resistant to GLH. IR26, IR36, IR50, and TNAU13613 showed moderate resistance. □

Insect resistance

Field evaluation of rice cultivars in India for resistance to brown planthopper (BPH)

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BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) causes serious damage to rice during rabi season (Dec-Jan to Mar-Apr) in Kuttanad area of Kerala State. Outbreaks have been reported since 1973. In 1986-87, rice crops were hopperburned.

We evaluated 42 rice accessions from the All India Coordinated Rice

Accessions rated as highly resistant, resistant, and moderately resistant to BPH. Kerala, India, 1986-87.

Designation	Cross combination	BPH damage score ^a (0-9)			Damage rating ^b
		1986 kharif	1987 rabi	Mean	
RP1579-52-47	Phalguna/ARC6650	1	1	1	HR
RP1579-28-54	Phalguna/ARC6650	1	1	1	HR
RP2068-18-3-1	IET5656/Velluthacheera	1	1	1	HR
IRP2068-18-4-5	IET5656/Velluthacheera	1	1	1	HR
RP1579-1585-28-205	Phalguna/ARC6650	1	1	1	HR
RP2547-1621-37-217	ARC5723/ARC6650//RP1579-38	1	1	1	HR
RP1976-18-6-4-2	IET5656/ARC6650	1	1	1	HR
RP1960-1569-24-224	IET5656/IET5688	1	1	1	HR
KAU153-1	IR1561/PTB33	3	1	2	R
RP2068-32-6-1	IET5656/Velluthacheera	5	5	5	MR
RP2084-2-3-1	Phalguna/NLR96 74	5	3	4	MR
RP2084-74-5-2	Phalguna/NLR96 74	6	3	4.5	MR
CR400-21-1-1	IR20/CR95-112-8	5	3	4	MR
Sonasali		5	5	5	MR
Phalguna		7	3	5	MR

^aBy Standard evaluation system for rice. ^bHR = highly resistant, R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant.